

INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL COMPETENCE AND ORGANIZATIONAL SKILLS TO JOB SATISFACTION AMONG TEACHER COORDINATORS IN SELECTED SCHOOLS

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Influence of Technological Competence and Organizational Skills to Job Satisfaction among Teacher Coordinators in Selected Schools

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Abstract

In the Philippines, overworked teachers prioritize non-teaching tasks over student learning, leading to poor teaching performance and job satisfaction. The purpose of this study was to investigate how teacher coordinators' job satisfaction was influenced by their organizational skills and technological competence. Descriptive-correlational quantitative research design with regression analysis was used in the study which involved 140 teacher coordinators from 21 selected public elementary schools in the district of Carmen in the Division of Davao del Norte. A random sampling technique was used to choose the study's respondents. The data was analyzed using regression analysis, mean, and Pearson-r. The findings showed that there is a very high level of technological competence with overall mean of 4.214(SD=0.525), a high level of organizational skills with overall mean of 4.18(SD=0.392), and a very high level of job satisfaction among teacher coordinators with an overall mean of 4.273(SD=0.495). Furthermore, the correlation between technological competence and job satisfaction is determined to be 0.388*, which is significant at 0.05 and organizational skills and job satisfaction have an r-value of 0.717*, which is significant at 0.05. Indicating a strong link between technological competence and organizational skills and job satisfaction. However, the regression analysis revealed technological competence has a probability of 0.893 was higher than the significance level of 0.05 and organizational skills has a beta of 0.712* and a corresponding p-value of 0.001, this implies that the technological competence does not significantly influence job satisfaction while organizational skills significantly influence the job satisfaction of teacher coordinators. Extraversion, decision making, fixed vs. growth, and job performance were revealed as the domains of organizational skills that influence job satisfaction. This suggests that educational policymakers, school heads and teacher coordinators can work together to escalate.

Keywords: MAED - Educational Management, technological competence, organizational skills, job satisfaction, teacher coordinators, Philippines

Introduction

Teacher job satisfaction is an issue in Southeast Asian (SEA) countries, including the Philippines. There is a rising concern that teachers, particularly in primary school, are becoming more demotivated, thus leads to poor teacher performance. This affects not just the teacher's quality of teaching, but also the teachers' and students' well-being, teacher retention, general school cohesiveness, and the teaching profession's status (Oblina et al., 2021). In addition, the study conducted by Hero (2020) revealed that apart from teaching loads, public elementary school teachers in the District of Obando, Bulacan, are overworked with workloads. Instead of reviewing and preparing their next lesson, teachers devote longer on non-teaching tasks. It indicates that today's educators are less focused on engaging students in learning and more concerned with meeting the paper-work deadlines.

The importance of studying job satisfaction provides favorable responds to the global problem of teacher shortage. Having a strong correlation with teacher retention, job satisfaction also benefits the general coherence of the school, the welfare of instructors and their students, and the standing of the teaching profession (Toropova & Johansson, 2020). Similarly, job satisfaction provides strong support to school systems because teacher with high job satisfaction are healthier, more productive, and more likely to stay in their positions over the long term, which is important given the global teacher shortage and high turnover rates in some nations (Dreer, 2021).

This study is anchored on Adams' Equity Theory of Motivation (Adams, 1965). This theory promotes the achievement of a just proportion between the inputs (e.g., education, hard work, skills level, intelligence, trainings) and outputs (e.g., pay, intrinsic rewards, job status, salary) of workers. The theory is predicated on the idea that when workers believe their inputs surpass their outputs, they lose interest in their work and their employer.

Technological competence is the first independent variable of this study and supported (Kundu et al., 2020), with the following indicators: teachers' ICT self-efficacy and teachers' perception of ICT infrastructure. Organizational skills serve as the second independent variable, as outlined by Hemani and Rashidi (2016). They identified several related indicators, including extraversion, workplace attitudes and behaviors, decision-making capabilities, achievement striving, mindset orientation (fixed vs. growth), multitasking proficiency, and overall job performance. Furthermore, job satisfaction is the dependent variable and supported by (Ogochi, 2011), with indicators of school policy and administration, salary, job security, work condition, and status/position.

The first independent variable was technological competence (Kundu et al., 2020), which has the following indicators, teachers' ICT self-efficacy, in this study, it pertains to the ability of the teacher coordinators in using computer-related tools, and teachers' perception of ICT infrastructure, in this study, it pertains to the perception of teacher coordinators about the provided support of the school in terms of trainings, ICT tools and facilities.

Second independent variable was organizational skills (Hemani & Rashidi 2016), which has the following indicators: extraversion, in this study pertains to the traits of the teachers as to sociable, lively, and active. Workplace attitude and behavior, in this study refers as a good mindset leads to positive behavior. Decision making, in this study pertains to the ability of the teacher to choose appropriate option out of the given alternatives to reach the best outcome. Achievement striving, in this study it refers as the degree to which the teacher works seriously and actively to improve performance. Fixed vs. growth, in this study pertains to the mindset of the teacher to improve and grow versus the fixed mindset that traits are inherently stable and unchangeable. Multitasking, in this study refers to the attitude of the teacher coordinator towards completing multiple tasks simultaneously. Job performance, in this study refers to the teacher coordinator's performance in reaching personal and organizational goals.

On the other hand, Ogochi (2011) studied job satisfaction as the dependent variable and has the following indicators: school policy and administration, in this study, it refers to the understanding of the teacher about the standard operating procedure of the school in terms of workplace culture, and administrator's appreciative skills in motivating teachers. Salary, in this study, includes equitable and adequate pay, additional monetary compensation, and time off pay of the teachers. Job security, in this study, pertains to the safe sense of knowing of the teachers with their work in terms of benefits for foreseeable future. Work condition, in this study, refers to the working environment teachers as influence by physical condition. Status/Position, in this study, includes aspects of self-fulfillment, recognition, and prestige.

As far as the researcher is aware, no study has examined the impact of organizational skills and technological competence on the job satisfaction of teacher coordinators in the Davao del Norte Division. By examining the connection between organizational skills and technological competence and job satisfaction, this study aims to bridge the empirical research gap and to look for factors that can be of help to the teachers to further increase their job satisfaction specially the teacher coordinators who handles multiple workloads. Thus, there is an urgency that this study is conducted to deeply investigate the job satisfaction of teacher coordinators.

This study holds worldwide significance as it underscores the impact of technological competence and organizational skills on job satisfaction among educators with multiple ancillary tasks. This study aimed to help and improve the level of job satisfaction of teacher coordinators in a way that it developed the existing level of professional skills to function in a manner that could improve their social standing (Khan, 2021). Moreover, school administrators in Davao del Norte evaluates teacher coordinators' conditions and assist them with task completion difficulties through professional development and training seminars. The study benefits the Department of Education by providing insights to enhance existing plans and programs aimed at enhancing teacher job satisfaction. More importantly, this study aims to spark future researchers' interest in teacher coordinators' experiences in managing various workloads, a crucial topic in education.

Research Objectives

The following objectives were the focus of this investigation:

1. To describe the level of technological competence of teacher coordinators in terms of Teachers' ICT self-efficacy and Teachers' perception of ICT infrastructure;
2. To describe the level of organizational skills of teacher coordinators in terms of extraversion, workplace attitude and behavior, decision making, achievement striving, fixed vs. growth, multitasking, and job performance; and,
3. To describe the level of job satisfaction of teacher coordinators in terms of school policy and administration, salary, job security, work condition, and status/position.
4. To determine the significant relationship existed between technological competence and job satisfaction of teacher coordinators;
5. To determine the significant relationship of organizational skills and job satisfaction of teacher coordinators;
6. To determine which domain of technological competence and organizational skills influence the job satisfaction among teacher coordinators.
7. To determine that there is no significant relationship between technological competence and job satisfaction;
8. To determine that there is no significant relationship between organizational skills and job satisfaction;
9. To determine that there is no domain of technological competence and organizational skills influence the job satisfaction among teacher coordinators.

Literature Review

The link between technological competence and organizational skills to the theoretical and empirical findings were presented to give the variables in this study a strong basis. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), first presented by Davis in 1989, served as the foundation for technological competency. This theory explains the acceptable manner of computers rely on how the teachers see its usefulness in their job. TAM is based on two fundamental ideas that perceived technology usefulness can increase a person's job performance; and by having perceived ease of use of technology, a user can be free of effort. In addition, technology influences education in a beneficial way thus, it is necessary for every nation to have a more technologically advanced education field in the future (Raja & Nagasubramani, 2018). Likewise, the research of Sapta et al., (2021) implies that technology has a favorable impact on employee motivation, it further stated that that the greater the usage of technology, the greater an employee's job satisfaction. This

research argued that technology is required to motivate employees to enhance their performance.

Meanwhile, organizational skills were based on Self-perception Theory by Bem (1972). This theory claimed that people evaluate their own behavior in the same manner as they interpret that of others, and each person's behavior is impacted by their social environment rather than their own free will. Primarily, this theory was recognized for its capacity to argue against an idea of cognitive dissonance by giving suggestions in the altering inconsistent thoughts to resolve conflict (Bem & McConnell, 1970). For example, if teacher does not like doing multitasking but constantly finds himself doing multitasking, he or she needs to change the belief to align it with the behavior. In fact, (Hemani & Rashidi, 2016) define organizational skills as the behavioral or non-cognitive abilities that an employee should possess. Indeed, a study measuring the organizational skills and its effect on teachers' academic optimism was conducted and it reveals that teachers should have attributes such as effective communication skills, lesson preparation, and superior time management abilities in order to optimize their teaching (Siddiqui et al., 2022). Similarly, personality traits like extraversion has a positive correlation in determining job satisfaction and crucial for the teachers and academic institutions. Extraversion and other important personality traits must be considered when creating procedures and policies meant to improve wellbeing and job satisfaction (Abdulai & Carvajal, 2023).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive correlational quantitative design along with regression analysis. Descriptive-correlational research design was appropriate for this study, which assessed the level of technological competence and organizational skills among teacher coordinators and its influence on job satisfaction. For obtaining information that give the target respondents a clear image of the event or subject being investigated, the quantitative approach is relevant and timely (Dudovskly, 2016).

Respondents

The study respondents were the 140 public elementary school teacher coordinators, specifically in Carmen District of the Division of Davao del Norte. The researcher considered the 21 public elementary schools in Carmen District where some of the teachers were observed having two or more coordinatorship, advisorship, and chairmanship. As an inclusion criterion in determining the respondents of the study, those teachers with coordinatorship, adviser ship, and chairmanship more preferably with actual designation signed by their school heads with more than one-year experience as teacher coordinator, adviser, and chairperson, as stated in in Deped Order No. 005 series of 2024 was recruited for the purpose of this study. Teachers who do not have ancillary services and those teachers from the private schools fall under the exclusion criteria and were not included in this study. Additionally, respondents had the option to withdraw at any time if they felt intimidated by the way the study was being administered.

Instrument

This study used downloaded, modified, and adopted questionnaire in gathering the data. A 5-point Likert scale measured the independent variables and dependent variable of this study, which the respondents rated honestly. The questionnaire on the level of technological competence (Kundu et al., 2020) was composed of two indicators: teachers' ICT self-efficacy and teachers' perception of ICT infrastructure. The questionnaire on the level of organizational skills (Hemani & Rashidi, 2016) was composed of seven indicators: extraversion, workplace attitude and behavior, decision making, achievement striving, fixed vs. growth, multitasking, and job performance. The questionnaire on the level of job satisfaction (Ogochi, 2011) of teacher coordinators was composed of five indicators: school policy and administration, salary, job security, work condition, and status/position. The questionnaire was validated by the panel of experts, both internal and external validators. The items were subjected into a pilot testing to attest its reliability and validity. The researcher was given statistician who guided in the conduct of pilot testing and Cronbach alpha for the validity and reliability of the items.

Procedure

The researcher requested permission to perform the study from the School Division Superintendent of the Department of Education Division of Davao del Norte. The researcher sent request letter to the district supervisors and the school principals of the respective target schools after obtaining the authorization, together with the replied endorsement from the Schools Division Superintendent for the actual conduct of the study. To start gathering data, the respondents were requested to complete the informed consent form and asked to answer the questions honestly. After the questionnaire were answered by the respondents, the researcher collected the data one week from the date of distribution as agreed upon. Lastly, data was tallied, eventually submitted the data to the statistician for data treatment and statistical analysis.

Ethical Considerations

A variety of ethical issues and problems that were specifically relevant to this quantitative investigation. Specifically, in maintaining both the correctness of the research study's conduct and the safety of the participants. The researcher followed the methodology, and the established criteria were closely applied in this investigation using the following: voluntary participation, privacy and confidentiality, informed consent process, recruitment, plagiarism, fabrication, permission from organization/location, and authorship.

Results and Discussion

Level of Technological Competence

The level of technological competence was measured in terms of the following: (1) teachers' ICT self-efficacy; and (2) teachers' perception of ICT infrastructure. Based on the given data, the general mean is 4.214 (SD=0.525) which can be described as very high. This implies that technological competence is very much observed.

Table 1. *Level of Technological Competence*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Teachers' ICT self-efficacy	4.351	0.579	Very High
Teachers' perception of ICT Infrastructure	4.077	0.644	High
Overall	4.214	0.525	Very High

Specifically, the indicator rated the highest was teachers' ICT self-efficacy with a mean of 4.351 (SD=0.579), described as very high and very much observed in connecting to the internet, using e-mail, web surfing, selecting suitable ICT tools for teaching and non-teaching tasks, and can work on personal computer with confidence.

Subsequently, the item with the lowest was teachers' perception of ICT infrastructure with a mean rating of 4.077 (SD=0.644), described as high and much observed in how the school keeps budget for implementation and maintenance of ICTs, motivates teachers to partake in ICT trainings, and inspires teachers to use ICT in completing teaching and non-teaching tasks.

Level of Organizational Skills

Table 2 presents the level of organizational skills in terms of the following: (1) extraversion; (2) workplace attitude and behavior; (3) decision making; (4) achievement striving; (5) fixed vs. growth; (6) multitasking; and (7) job performance. It can be gleaned from the table that the overall mean level of organizational skills is 4.18 (SD=0.392), which has a verbal equivalent of high. This means that the organizational skills of the teacher coordinators are much observed.

Specifically, the indicator with the highest mean was decision making with mean score of 4.503 (SD=0.419), described as very high and very much observed in thinking carefully before making an important decision, doing things that relates to their future, asking for help when they don't understand something, considers all of the implications before making decisions, and remain calm when they have to make decisions very quickly.

On the other hand, the indicators with the lowest means are: multitasking, workplace attitude and behavior, and extraversion. Multitasking with mean score of 3.738 (SD=0.812) described as high and much observed especially in breaking tasks into smaller parts and switching to other tasks occasionally, working on several projects in a day, rather than completing one project and then switching to another and, working in a job where they were constantly shifting from one task to another.

Also, workplace attitude and behavior with a mean score of 3.911 (SD=0.662) described as high and much observed especially in how teacher coordinators think that other people take advantage of them. Lastly, extraversion with mean score of 4.146 (SD=0.59) describe as high and much observed among teacher coordinators especially in talking loudly about their needs to anyone.

Table 2. *Level of Organizational Skills*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Extraversion	4.146	0.59	High
Workplace Attitude and Behavior	3.911	0.662	High
Decision Making	4.503	0.419	Very High
Achievement Striving	4.323	0.493	Very High
Fixed Vs. Growth	4.259	0.485	Very High
Multitasking	3.738	0.812	High
Job Performance	4.378	0.499	Very High
Overall	4.18	0.392	High

Level of Job Satisfaction

Table 3 presents the level of job satisfaction terms of the following: (1) school policies and administration; (2) salary; (3) job security; (4) work condition; and (5) status/position. The overall mean score is 4.273 (SD=0.495), described as very high. This means that the job satisfaction of teacher coordinators is very much observed.

Specifically, the indicator with the highest mean was status/position with mean score of 4.43 (SD=0.495), described as very high and very much observed in participating in the determination of teaching-learning methods and procedures, receiving respect from students, using unique capabilities and potentials to move up in the profession like being promoted someday, experiencing prestige from the community members, and getting high regard from colleagues.

Table 3. *Level of Job Satisfaction*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Equivalent
School Policies and Administration	4.286	0.521	Very High
Salary	4.303	0.673	Very High
Job Security	4.011	0.747	High
Work Condition	4.334	0.575	Very High
Status/Position	4.43	0.52	Very High
Overall	4.273	0.495	Very High

Moreover, job security got the lowest mean score of 4.011 (SD=0.747), described as high and much observed on their work especially in feeling content with their medical insurance and feeling secure with accidental health insurance.

Significant Relationship between Technological Competence, Organizational Skills and Job Satisfaction

Table 4 shows a substantial association between technological competence and organizational skills and job satisfaction, which was examined at the 0.05 level of significance. Each independent variable was measured against the level of job satisfaction. The correlation between technological competence and job satisfaction is determined to be 0.388*, which is significant at 0.05. Additionally, organizational skills and job satisfaction have an r-value of 0.717*, which is significant at 0.05. The findings revealed that there is a strong link between technological competence and organizational skills and job satisfaction.

Table 4. *Relationship between Technological Competence and Organizational Skills to Job Satisfaction*

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	r-value	r ²	p-value	Decision
Technological Competence		0.388*	0.151	<.001	Reject H0
Organizational Skills	Job Satisfaction	0.717*	0.514	<.001	Reject H0

*p<0.05

The positive value of the Pearson r showed a direct relationship between technological competence and organizational skills to job satisfaction. As the teacher coordinators' technological competence and organizational skills increase, their job satisfaction also increases. If teacher coordinators' technological skills and organizational skills decrease, job satisfaction also decreases.

Significant Relationship between Technological Competence and Job Satisfaction

Table 4.1 shows a substantial connection between technological skill and job satisfaction. This was assessed at the 0.05 threshold of significance. Each indication of technological competence was assessed against job satisfaction.

Teachers' ICT self-efficacy has a probability level of <.001, and teachers' assessment of ICT infrastructure has a probability of 0.005, both with a level of significance below 0.05. Thus, the first null hypothesis, claiming that there is no substantial connection between technological competence and job satisfaction, is rejected. This means that markers of technological competence are positively and significantly related to job satisfaction.

Table 4.1. *Relationship between Technological Competence and Job Satisfaction*

Indicators	Dependent Variable	r-value	r ²	p-value	Decision
Teachers' ICT self-efficacy		0.443*	0.196	<.001	Reject H0
Teachers' perception of ICT Infrastructure	Job Satisfaction	0.235*	0.055	0.005	Reject H0

*p<0.05

Significant Relationship between Organizational Skills and Job Satisfaction

The strong correlation between job satisfaction and organizational abilities is shown in Table 4.2. The significance level for this test was set at 0.05. The degree of job satisfaction was compared to each of the metrics under organizational skills. The findings demonstrated a positive and substantial relationship between job satisfaction and each of the seven indicators in the organizational skills. Since the p-value for each of the seven variables is less than 0.05, the second null hypothesis, which claims that there is no significant correlation between job satisfaction and organizational skills, is thus rejected. This suggests that job satisfaction and organizational skills indicators are positively and significantly correlated.

Table 4.2. *Relationship between Organizational Skills and Job Satisfaction*

Indicators	Dependent Variable	r-value	r ²	p-value	Decision
Extraversion		0.517*	0.267	<.001	Reject H0
Workplace Attitude and Behavior		0.412*	0.17	<.001	Reject H0
Decision Making		0.572*	0.307	<.001	Reject H0
Achievement Striving	Job Satisfaction	0.546*	0.298	<.001	Reject H0
Fived Vs. Growth		0.652*	0.425	<.001	Reject H0
Multitasking		0.355*	0.126	<.001	Reject H0
Job Performance		0.559*	0.312	<.001	Reject H0

Regression Analysis on the Influence of Technological Competence and Organizational skills to Job Satisfaction

Table 5 shows the results of a regression study examining the relationship between the two independent variables—technological competence and organizational skills—and the dependent variable, teacher coordinators' job satisfaction. With a beta of 0.009 and a p-value of 0.893, the results demonstrated the degree of change in each of the variables. This suggests that technological competence had no effect on job satisfaction because its probability of 0.893 was higher than the significance level of 0.05. However, the second variable, organizational skills, has a beta of 0.712* and a corresponding p-value of 0.001, indicating that it had an impact on job satisfaction because its probability was less than 0.05 ($p < .001$). This implies that the technological competence does not significantly influence job satisfaction while organizational skills significantly influence the job satisfaction of teacher coordinators.

Table 5. Regression Analysis on the influence of Technological Competence and Organizational Skills to Job Satisfaction

Indicators	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision
	B	SE				
(constant)	0.476	0.326				
Technological Competence	0.009	0.066	0.009	0.135	0.893	Do not Reject H0
Organizational Skills	0.899	0.089	0.712*	10.121	<.001	Reject H0

Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction
 * $p < 0.05$ R=0.717 R²= 0.514 F-value= 72.48 p-value= <0.001

Regression Analysis on the influence of the domains of Organizational Skills to Job Satisfaction

Table 5.1 presents the regression analysis of the organizational skills domains' impact on job satisfaction among teacher. With a computed F-ratio of 28.735 and a p-value of 0.0001, the results indicated a substantial correlation between teacher coordinators' job satisfaction and organizational abilities. The R-value of 0.777 suggests that job satisfaction and organizational skills are positively correlated. The categories of extraversion, workplace attitude and behavior, decision making, achievement striving, fixed vs. growth, multitasking, and job performance account for 60.4% of the teacher coordinators' overall R² of 0.604.

The four organizational skills domains are as follows: job performance has a beta of 0.212* and a corresponding p-value of 0.003, fixed vs. growth has a beta of 0.232* and a corresponding p-value of 0.011, decision making has a beta of 0.267* and a p-value of <.001, and extraversion has a beta of 0.221* and a p-value of <.001. Given that each of the four domains has a probability below the 0.05 level of significance, it can be concluded that they have a substantial impact on job satisfaction.

Additionally, three organizational skills domains—workplace attitude and behavior, achievement striving, and multitasking—have p-values greater than 0.05, meaning they do not substantially affect job satisfaction. The p-value is 0.055 and the beta is 0.143 for the workplace attitude and behavior domain. The next domain, achievement striving, has a p-value of 0.591 and a beta of 0.042. The last domain, multitasking, has a p-value of 0.61 and a beta of -0.039. The result signifies that the three domains have no significant influence on job satisfaction among teacher coordinators. Hence, job satisfaction will improve more on extraversion, decision making, fixed vs. growth and job performance and not much on workplace attitude and behavior, achievement striving and multitasking. Additionally, the hypothesis which states that there is no domain in organizational skills influence the job satisfaction of teacher coordinators is rejected on four domains namely: extraversion, decision making, fixed vs. growth and job performance. While the three domains evidently shown on the table and to answer the hypothesis that there is no domain in organizational skills that influence the job satisfaction among teacher coordinators is not rejected.

Table 5.1. Regression Analysis on the influence of the domains of Organizational Skills to Job Satisfaction

Indicators	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision
	B	SE				
(constant)	-0.358	0.339				
Extraversion	0.185	0.055	0.221*	3.391	<.001	Reject H0
Workplace Attitude and Behavior	0.107	0.056	0.143	1.932	0.055	Do not Reject H0
Decision Making	0.316	0.08	0.267*	3.958	<.001	Reject H0
Achievement Striving	0.042	0.078	0.042	0.539	0.591	Do not Reject H0
Fixed Vs. Growth	0.237	0.092	0.232*	2.578	0.011	Reject H0
Multitasking	-0.024	0.046	-0.039	-0.511	0.611	Do not Reject H0
Job Performance	0.21	0.07	0.212*	2.994	0.003	Reject H0

Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction
 * $p < 0.05$ R=0.777 R²= 0.604 F-value= 28.735 p-value= <.001

Conclusions

As the study's findings reveal, conclusions are made in this section. The findings revealed that the level of technological competence in terms of teachers' ICT self-efficacy and teachers' perception of ICT infrastructure was very high and very much observed. In

addition, the organizational skills in terms of extraversion, workplace attitude and behavior, decision making, achievement striving, fixed vs. growth, multitasking, and job performance was high and much observed. Furthermore, job satisfaction in terms of school policies and administration, salary, work condition and status/position with a very high mean and very much observed. The findings also show a strong correlation between job satisfaction and organizational skills and technological competence. Whereas organizational skills had a major impact on teacher coordinators' job satisfaction, technological competence had little effect.

Moreover, all of the indicators under technological competence has significant relationship to job satisfaction. Similarly, there is a strong correlation between job satisfaction and all indicators under organizational skills. Additionally, the four domains under organizational skills namely: extraversion, decision making, fixed vs. growth, and job performance significantly influence job satisfaction. However, workplace attitude and behavior, achievement striving, and multitasking do not influence the job satisfaction of teacher coordinators.

The outcomes of this inquest further confirm the Adam's Equity Theory of Motivation on the appropriate ratio between inputs and outputs in the workplace. Teacher coordinators needs to maintain their high level of competencies and skills that are essential with their workloads in order for them to continue their very high job satisfaction ratings. School leaders might as well avoid inequity within the organization that can affect the perceived sense of balance (inputs and outputs) for this can affect the teacher coordinators sense of motivation. Instead, equity must be implemented within the organization by making them feel the prestige as well as the feeling of being respected in the workplace, provide just and right pay to help them feel secure with their job and let them partake in decision-making in the school.

The researcher offers the following suggestions in light of the study's results and conclusion for technological competence, organizational skills, and job satisfaction. The Division of Davao del Norte's administrators may offer sufficient ICT equipment and facilities to enable utilization of ICT among teacher coordinators. Additionally, every school may have a sustainable allocation for ICT adoption and servicing. This may help teacher coordinators to improve their level of perception about ICT infrastructure at school.

Furthermore, workplace attitude and behavior may enhance by developing effective dynamic work system so that teacher coordinators may think that they are not taken advantage at work. School heads and administrators may encourage loud and spontaneous discussions among teacher coordinators to address and improve the level of extraversion. In addition, teacher coordinators may engage in trainings and seminars to handle properly multiple assigned task especially on switching back and forth between multiple assignments rather than completing them one at a time.

Moreover, job security, the lowest mean level of job satisfaction among teacher coordinators. The Department of Education (DepEd) may review the policy and benefit packages of teacher coordinators especially the medical insurance and accidental death insurance. Improved health insurance benefits among teacher coordinators that may protect them from unexpected high medical bills and costs. Also, the enhanced policy on accidental death insurance of teacher coordinators may increase their sense of security with the unforeseeable unfortunate events.

Finally, future researchers may consider exploring the technological competence and organizational skills and the influence to job satisfaction among teacher coordinators for this may help them to stay inspired to become more efficient with their special obligations in school. Future studies may examine more factors that could potentially mitigate the strong correlation between technological competence and organizational skills to job satisfaction that may be essential data for the field of research.

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